

Seed drill for upland rice grown in undulating terrain

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We tested four seed drills and two other conventional seeding practices (see table) for upland rice during three wet seasons (1995-97) in a randomized block design with three replications.

The soil was a lateritic, coarse-textured, well-drained sandy loam with pH 5.2, 0.03% total N, 20 kg available P ha⁻¹, 220 kg available K ha⁻¹, 13.1% field capacity, and 9.5% wilting point by weight basis. Rice variety Heera (85 d duration) was dry-seeded at 75 kg seeds ha⁻¹ with 60-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹. All P and K and 25% N were applied at sowing; 50% N was topdressed 20 d after sowing (DAS), with 25% N at 40 DAS.

Data on average depth of seed placement, seed population m², energy used for seeding, and grain yield are given in the table.

The highest rice grain yield (2.5 t ha⁻¹) was observed using T2 (Gujarat State Fertilizer Corporation seed-cum-fertilizer drill) (see figure). Broadcasting (T6) had the lowest yield (1.5 t ha⁻¹) and the highest energy requirement (360 MJ ha⁻¹) during seeding. The shallow seed depth resulted in poor crop stand.

Performance parameters of seed drills.

Treatment	Seed placement depth (cm)	Seed population m ² (no.)	Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Energy use (MJ ha ⁻¹)
T1-Implement factory seed drill (3-row, hand-drawn)	2.83	210	2.1	66.7
T2-Gujarat State Fertilizer Corp. seed-cum-fertilizer drill (2-row, bullock-drawn)	2.65	233	2.5	266.4
T3-Implement factory seed drill (1-row, bullock-drawn)	2.15	196	2.2	374.6
T4-Annapurna seed drill (5-row, hand-drawn)	1.22	173	2.3	378.4
T5-Sowing behind the plow	2.17	179	1.9	121.5
T6-Broadcasting	1.30	125	1.5	360.0

Note: Seed rate was 75 kg ha⁻¹ for all treatments.

The Gujarat State Fertilizer Corporation seed-cum-fertilizer drill.

Rolling marker for a rice field

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Ninety-five percent of rice farmers in South Sulawesi, Indonesia, transplant rice using a traditional marker called a *caplak*. The marker is shaped and works like a traditional harrow. When it is pulled forward, it leaves straight-line marks on the soil. The

marker should then be pulled again at right angles to mark the planting row.

A new rolling marker (see figure) was designed which, in contrast to the traditional system, will indicate the points for planting when pulled only once. Straight

lines are made by the wheels and cross lines are made by the outer beams.

To simplify the tool, wheel circumference was fixed at 100 cm. Each wheel was then divided by 4 or 5 to give a distance of 25 or 20 cm. The six wheels are

The rolling marker.

The new rolling marker provides an easy system for marking planting distances.

connected by flat outer beams that make the straight lines at 25 or 20 cm.

The use of the roller provides an easy system for marking 20 × 20-cm, 20 × 25-cm, or 25 × 25-cm planting distances. These different distances are achieved by changing the outer beam from four to five pieces or by shifting the movable wheels and joining the two wheels in the center together to make a distance of 25 × 25 cm. The marker is efficient because it makes cross lines as planting markers in only one pass. The marker is also lighter and has less soil draft than the traditional marker.

The materials required to construct a rolling marker are (1) a 5-m-long wood beam (3 × 4 cm) for the axis and outer beam, (2) a 5-m-long wood beam (20 × 2 cm) for the six-piece wheels, (3) a 2-m-long L-shaped iron (0.5-inch) for the frame (wood can be used if necessary), and (4) two bearings for the wheels.

A modified area sampler for aquatic invertebrate assemblages in flooded rice

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Takahashi et al (1982) invented a two-enclosure "area sampler" for sampling floodwater invertebrates in California rice fields. In this note, we report on some design modifications and performance characteristics of the area sampler (hereafter called floodwater collector) for use in tropical irrigated rice fields.

Our version uses a pair of metal cylinders (instead of two square boxes used by Takahashi et al), one serving as an outer cylinder made from galvanized tin ("A" cylinder), and an inner cylinder ("B" cylinder) functioning as a plunger made from stainless steel (see figure). Cylinder A is bottomless with fifteen 3.3-cm holes drilled along its bottom edge to allow passage of aquatic invertebrates. It is fitted with a 7.5-cm-wide collar that functions as a hole cover and adjustable clamp during sam-

pling. Cylinder B has two handles and a central 5-cm hole in its bottom to accommodate a #11 rubber stopper. Multiple units of cylinder A can be made as needed to obtain the desired sample size; however, only one unit of cylinder B is required. The diameter of the collector can be adjusted to fit local planting practices. No matter what diameter is used, water volume must be recorded for each sample to obtain population density estimates.

The field operation of our collector requires 2 consecutive days: the first day to sink the A cylinders in the field, and the second day to take samples. On day 1, the A cylinders are centered over single rice plants (or hills) and collars are clamped above the 15 access holes. The passage of 1 d between placement and collection allows water and organisms to reequilibrate

in the field following initial disturbance. (Takahashi et al located and gathered their samples all on the same day.) On day 2, the collars are lowered and clamped tightly around the access holes to prevent escape of invertebrates. The rice plant is removed, rinsed to remove attached invertebrates, and set aside. Next, the operator grasps the B cylinder by the handles and plunges it into the A cylinder to expel water and trapped organisms through the 5-cm hole. After expelling all the remaining water, the operator inserts the rubber stopper into the B cylinder and pulls it out while standing on the metal supports of the A cylinder.

Inspecting the mud for additional invertebrates underneath the B cylinder will ensure a more representative catch. Depending on water depth and season,